

THE IMPORTANCE OF NATURAL SCIENCES IN DEVELOPING CREATIVITY AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article highlights the role and importance of natural sciences in developing creativity among primary school teachers. It is substantiated that teaching natural sciences enhances creative thinking, problem-solving skills, and independent decision-making abilities. The study also analyzes methods of fostering a creative approach through modern pedagogical technologies. The findings of the research contribute to improving the professional competence of teachers in primary education.*

Keywords: *didactic approaches, abundance of ideas, experiences, observations, and collaborative discussions.*

Introduction

The primary education system is regarded as a foundational stage that ensures learners' success in subsequent levels of education, as well as the formation of their scientific worldview and problem-solving culture. In particular, the content of natural sciences enhances young learners' observational skills, causal reasoning, the ability to draw evidence-based conclusions, and motivation for learning through practical experimentation.

However, in 21st-century education, the mere transmission of knowledge is no longer sufficient; fostering students' creative thinking, organizing activities aimed at generating and testing new ideas, has become one of the key requirements. Creativity, in turn, does not emerge spontaneously. It is developed through purposeful didactic approaches, teaching methods, learning environments, assessment practices, and a culture of reflection.

Therefore, it is essential to develop in prospective primary school teachers the competencies to organize lessons using methods that foster creativity in natural science classes, to perceive creativity as a pedagogical objective, to adapt lesson design accordingly, and to engage students in the process of "discovery" (UNESCO, 2015).

In scientific literature, creativity is often interpreted as the ability to generate novel and valuable (useful, appropriate, and socially acceptable) ideas; it encompasses such components as divergent thinking, problem sensitivity, hypothesis generation, a willingness to take risks and learn from errors, experimentation, and the ability to justify one's ideas. In the context of practical education, creativity is not limited to the mere "abundance of ideas," but also includes the application of ideas to real-life situations, their verification through experimentation, analysis of results, and subsequent cycles of refinement and improvement.

In primary science education, this is manifested, for example, through questions such as "Why do leaves turn yellow in autumn?", "Why does ice float on water?", and "Why are some objects attracted to magnets while others are not?", which guide students toward observation,

experimentation, modeling, and explanation. Therefore, when planning creative lessons, a prospective teacher should strive not merely to compile a set of engaging activities, but to design learning experiences that reveal the fundamental logic of scientific inquiry.

One of the effective ways to develop creativity in primary education is to strengthen the learner's role as an active subject of cognition based on the constructivist approach. In this context, knowledge is not delivered in a ready-made form; rather, learners "construct" understanding through their own experiences, observations, and collaborative discussions. Constructivist didactics recommends organizing the lesson as a последовательный process that begins with a problem situation, followed by eliciting students' hypotheses, gathering evidence, and arriving at conclusions.

This process naturally stimulates creative thinking, as at each stage learners propose their own ideas, justify them, and engage in discussion. In particular, Lev Vygotsky's concept of the "zone of proximal development" serves as an important methodological foundation for prospective teachers. Through guiding questions, prompts, modeling, and collaborative activities, the teacher supports learners in accomplishing tasks slightly beyond their current level of competence. Such pedagogical scaffolding also fosters creativity, as students move closer to independent problem-solving while receiving appropriate support at critical moments.

Within the framework of developing creative abilities, the first important direction for prospective teachers is mastering problem posing and problem-based learning methods. In problem-based instruction, the teacher does not lead students directly to ready-made answers; instead, they organize the stages of understanding the problem, breaking it down into components, formulating hypotheses, collecting evidence, and testing these hypotheses.

The content of natural sciences is particularly suitable for creating problem situations: through simple experiments, observation of natural phenomena, and everyday "why?" questions, problems emerge naturally. For example, in answering the question "Why does a wet towel dry faster in the sun but more slowly in the shade?", students discover factors such as temperature, airflow, and evaporation. The teacher, in turn, creates opportunities for students themselves to propose the conditions of the experiment.

Problem-based learning fosters creativity in two ways: on the one hand, through divergent thinking (generating multiple hypotheses), and on the other hand, through convergent thinking (selecting the most substantiated solution) (Ellis Paul Torrance, 1974).

The second direction involves developing a culture of questioning and designing teacher questions in a way that stimulates creativity. If classroom questions are limited to "yes/no" responses or mere recall of facts, the psychological space for creativity becomes restricted. Therefore, prospective teachers should employ higher-order questions such as "How can...?", "What would happen if...?", "Under what conditions...?", "Do you think there is another way?", and "How would you prove the result?", as well as teach students to formulate their own questions.

In this regard, Benjamin Bloom's taxonomy provides a useful framework for structuring questions according to levels of complexity: progressing from understanding and application to analysis, evaluation, and creation supports the development of creativity (Bloom, 1956). For example, instead of asking "List the three states of water" (recall), a more creativity-oriented question would be "Design an experiment to determine under which conditions water evaporates more quickly," which encourages inquiry and exploration.

The third direction involves organizing experiments and practical activities in a manner that is age-appropriate, safe, and goal-oriented. In natural science lessons, creativity often emerges

through the design of experiments. Learners determine what tools are needed to test their hypotheses, which variables should be controlled, and how results should be measured and recorded. This process represents a simplified form of the scientific method and fosters the development of scientific literacy as well as the initial skills of creative engineering thinking.

The inquiry-based learning approach is specifically grounded in this process. Within this framework, students ask questions, formulate hypotheses, test them, analyze results, and defend their conclusions through communication. Prospective teachers should learn to structure experiments not as fixed “instructions,” but as a “discovery laboratory.” For example, leaving multiple pathways open to achieve the same outcome, comparing different student-designed approaches, and even analyzing “incorrect” results. Indeed, the analysis of errors activates a crucial component of creativity-metacognitive reflection.

The fourth direction focuses on developing creative collaboration and communicative competencies. Creativity is often enhanced within social processes, through the exchange of ideas and collective discussions. Primary school students, by working in groups, learn to compare observational results, express their thoughts in simple language, provide evidence, and listen to others. A prospective teacher should perceive group work not as mere “noise,” but as structured scientific communication, ensuring clear role distribution (observer, recorder, presenter, materials manager), effective time management, and well-defined assessment criteria. In this process, creating a socio-psychological environment that fosters creativity-such as a safe atmosphere, respect for all ideas without ridicule, and maintaining an “idea bank”-is of particular importance.

The fifth direction involves strengthening creativity through an integrative (interdisciplinary) approach. Connecting natural science lessons with language arts (text construction, explanatory writing), mathematics (measurement, tables, diagrams), visual arts (models, drawings), and technology (simple devices) enhances students’ ability to transfer knowledge across domains, which is a key indicator of creative thinking.

In contemporary education, the STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, Mathematics) approach systematically promotes such integration. Within this framework, students solve problems using scientific concepts and engineering design, while presenting results in aesthetically and communicatively meaningful ways (Yakman, 2008). At the primary education level, STEAM does not require complex technologies. For example, simple projects such as “Building a bridge model” (using paper, sticks, and string) or “Water filtration” (using sand, cotton, and gravel) can effectively foster interdisciplinary creative activity.

In conclusion, the development of creativity in the process of teaching natural sciences largely depends on the teacher’s methodological approach. Meaningful questioning, hands-on experimentation, inquiry-based activities, and a collaborative learning environment contribute to the formation of students’ independent thinking and their ability to generate innovative ideas. Furthermore, an integrative approach based on STEAM expands opportunities for applying knowledge across different disciplines, thereby further enhancing creative thinking.

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